

Decisions, decisions

Where to Start When Managing Invasive Plants?

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Introduction

- Acacia species are some of the most widespread and problematic invasive alien species in Portugal.
- Due to the area invaded, *A. dealbata*, *A. melanoxylon*, *A. longifolia* and *A. saligna* are considered the most aggressive ones.
- Most management actions have been unsuccessful – urgent need for innovative approaches to improve their efficiency.

Study Area

Nature Reserves with areas invaded by *Acacia* spp. but with distinct set of biophysical and socio-environmental conditions.

1 - National Park of Peneda-Gerês

2 - Natural Park of Sintra-Cascais

3 - Arriba Fóssil da C. da Caparica

Fig. 1 – Map of Portuguese nature reserves.

Methods

At least one workshop will be held in April 2013 by a range of experts and stakeholders – academics, field managers, landowners, etc. Two methods will be used to obtain the objectives:

- The DPSIR framework (Driving forces-Pressure-State-Impacts-Responses) – to discuss and synthesize information mostly derived from experimental research;
- The AHP tool (Analytic Hierarchy Process) – to integrate information gathered from management experiences on the ground.

Aim & objectives

Develop decision-making tools to assist setting priorities for effective management of four invasive *Acacia* species starting at three nature reserves, but extending to the rest of Portugal.

- Identify invasion multiple drivers and how they are linked together;
- Identify main management constraints;
- Identify and quantify the importance of key factors;
- Create a priority map for sustainable management in the study areas;
- Propose a standardized prioritization scheme for management of other areas.

Results

Fig. 2 – The DPSIR framework for conceptualizing the dynamics of *Acacia* stands in the nature reserves (source Roura-Pascual et al. 2009).

Conclusion

Prioritizing control operations is essential for managing invasive plants such as *Acacia*. However assessing the effectiveness and consequences of these actions under different budgetary and temporal contexts is also vital.

Fig. 3 – Map of prioritize areas in Gerês.

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References:

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